

Important concerns arising from Jiang, G., Zhang, Y., Chen, M. et al.'s study titled "Effects of plant tissue permeability on invasion and population bottlenecks of a phytopathogen," published in *Nature Communications* 15, 62 (2024)

Vicente S. and Peeters N.

Université de Toulouse, INRAE, CNRS, Laboratoire des Interactions Plantes Micro-organismes Environnement (LIPME), 31326, Castanet-Tolosan

Email for correspondence: nemo.peeters@inrae.fr

Summary

After careful examination of the recently published paper of Jiang *et al.*, we have identified numerous and significant issues with the data and analysis presented in this study¹. Here we highlight missing data, duplicated values, erased information, misattribution of samples between replicates, and an overall inability to reproduce the analysis using the provided raw data.

These critical concerns undermine the validity of the reported results. We caution readers to interpret these findings with scepticism, considering them preliminary and potentially erroneous in their conclusions. We strongly urge the authors to review our concerns, which should probably lead them to retract this article.

Our analysis of the data published (and available as Supplementary Material) in the paper led to the identification of some important issues outlined in section 1 and 2. We then wanted to inspect the raw data available through a data repository and found some new important issues outlined in section 3 and 4.

1) Missing bacterial load data.

To the best of our knowledge, all comparable publications using the recently developed STAMP approach²⁻⁸ have collectively presented bottleneck values alongside corresponding bacterial load data for each sample analysed. These studies have consistently demonstrated the significance of integrating these findings to glean crucial insights into pathogen dynamics *in vivo*. It is our contention that the reviewer of the present paper should have insisted upon the provision of this essential data. Furthermore, we highlight that Jiang *et al.* stated having generated these data, yet they were never made available (see "Methods" section of study¹). We strongly urge the authors of the current study to provide the bacterial load data for every sample examined in their work, provided that such data were indeed collected concurrently with the STAMP data acquisition process.

2) Anomalies in the provided dataset ("Dataset2" in Supplementary Material of study¹) used for Figure 3¹ and concerns with subsequent statistical analysis.

Duplicated Inocula: It has come to our attention that although 24 inocula were mentioned (In01 to In24), in reality, these 24 inocula correspond to just 6 unique inocula (In01 to In06) duplicated 4 times (see Dataset2 in Supplementary material of study¹). We strongly recommend that the authors clarify that only 6 inocula were employed to generate all biological replicates, rather than 12 per group of resistant/susceptible plants.

Bottleneck Calculation Errors and Inconsistencies: We have identified a high number of samples (AC: 15, 17, 21, 22, 23, 25, 27, 28, 29, 31, 33, 34, 35 and HW: 13, 15, 17, 21, 22, 23, 25, 27, 29, 31, 33, 35) with non-zero barcode counts associated to inocula (In01, In03, In04, In05) for which the corresponding barcode counts are at zero reads. The only explanation for this discrepancy would involve a barcode

with a frequency below the detection threshold of the sequencing process emerging in the samples. Considering the obtained depths of sequencing in inocula (> 30000 reads), the probability of such an event is highly unlikely. This strongly suggests misattribution of the sample/inoculum pairs mentioned. Additionally, several other barcodes present in low quantities in the inocula (1 or 2 reads) would also require scrutiny. Since the formula for bottleneck calculation² does not accommodate a barcode with 0 reads in the inoculum, we were curious about the authors' approach. Upon examination of the provided R code (in Code Availability¹), we observed that bottleneck values were never calculated but instead provided as-is in an embedded file labelled "metafile.txt". Consequently, the validity of subsequent statistical analyses is also questionable.

Duplicated Data Points: Upon review, we observed that the cohort comprising 12 plants under the condition 'Hawai7996 xylem injection' (samples HW25 to HW36) actually consists of an exact numerical duplication of only 6 samples (HW25 to HW30). To say the least, this constitutes a clear breach of standard practices and introduces erroneous assumptions into subsequent statistical analyses. This duplication can be suspected when inspecting Fig3b panel DXI¹ and is obvious in Dataset2 (Supplementary Material of study¹).

Low Sequencing Depth of Samples: Notably, two samples (HW01 and HW02) exhibit a low and inadequate² depth of sequencing (~300 reads). Initially, we speculated a potential technical issue during the sequencing process for these samples. However, upon closer examination, a more troubling explanation emerged (see below).

Duplicated barcode: Two barcodes (t35 and t38) have the exact same region of variability as well as exact duplications of counts among samples. These two barcodes should be considered as one unique barcode or risk producing biases in the calculation of bottleneck values.

Inappropriate Statistical analysis: Upon review of Fig3b¹, it came to our attention that four conditions ("susceptible WR", "susceptible DXI", "resistant IR" and "resistant WR") significantly strayed from the normal distribution (Shapiro-Wilk test $p < 0.01$). Likewise, homoscedasticity was not verified for these groups (Levene test $p < 0.01$). Additionally, groups of samples of 12 (or 6 in the case of data duplication in condition "resistant DXI") are under the empirically accepted "20 to 30 samples" rule of thumb. As we see it, three statistical assumptions were violated with the use of a parametric ANOVA test in Fig3b¹ and we consider any subsequent interpretations as potentially erroneous and misleading.

3) Discrepancies between the raw data and the analysed data.

Given the numerous anomalies identified in the provided dataset, as detailed in Section 2, we opted to undertake a re-analysis of the raw data, which is available as Supplementary Material from a repository datacenter (ID: PRJCA016125, National Genomics Data Center of China). We processed the reads following the protocol outlined¹. First, we observed that the barcode region of variability spans 30 base pairs, contrary to the stated 25 base pairs. Subsequently, we conducted a mapping of the raw sequences against the list of 89 barcodes (excluding duplicate barcode t38), yielding results akin to those provided in the initial Dataset¹. This analysis revealed two significant discrepancies:

- a) Firstly, we identified a considerable number of unused reads corresponding to concealed barcodes. We re-align these reads against a reference sequence containing a (N)30 stretch in the region of variability (Reference_read_30N.fasta, Supplementary Material). To our astonishment, we identified 7 new barcodes in addition to the original 89 barcodes (refer to New_barcodes.fasta in Supplementary Material). We are confident that these reads correspond to existing barcodes and not to artefacts stemming from mutations or

sequencing errors. Indeed, these reads exhibit identical sequences (outside of the 30 bp diversity zone, reads length of 302 bp) and quality compared to the other 89 barcodes. Additionally, the maximum identity between barcodes is 17 bp in the region of variability. This makes the emergence of these barcodes impossible by mutations or sequencing errors alone. Using the raw data, we aligned the sequence data against the newly curated list of 96 barcodes and determined the proportion of reads that were previously overlooked (refer to Table1 in Supplementary Material). These "invisible barcodes" account for between 1% and 41% of the total sequencing depth of the samples. Notably, two extreme samples (HW01 and HW02, identified previously) see 99% of their sequencing reads corresponding to these barcodes, correcting their previous anomalous sequencing depth (see paragraph 2) and Table1). We find no justification for this data omission and once again regard it as a clear breach of standard practices. The exclusion of these barcodes introduces multiple biases and compromises the validity of the calculated bottleneck values. As a supplementary observation, upon re-analysis, one inoculum (In08) appears to be primarily composed of two barcodes, indicating it may be a sample rather than an inoculum.

- b) Secondly, analysing the raw data, we identified new inocula and sample sequence data absent from the analysed dataset (Dataset2 in Supplementary Material of study¹). Indeed, when mapping all the raw data against the new 96 barcodes, we were astonished to find complete new sequence information (not just for the new barcodes) corresponding to some inocula (In07 to In24) and samples (HW31 to HW36), as described in section 2, that were overwritten by the exact duplications identified in the analysed dataset (Dataset2 in Supplementary material of study¹). This newly generated mapped dataset is available here as Table1 in Supplementary Material. Why were inocula and samples duplicated when the original raw data seems to contain non-duplicated data? Which data is at the origin of the bottleneck calculations at the heart of this work?

4) inoculum-sample correspondence discrepancies in the New Dataset

Based on the information available in the study, we managed to generate a corrected dataset (Table1, Supplementary Material). Seeing how many different data discrepancies were identified in this process, we wanted to further inspect this new dataset before using it to run the bottleneck analysis and test the validity of the conclusions of the current study¹.

This prompted us to investigate the association between inocula and samples. Our rationale stems from the notion that each inoculum possesses a unique "barcode frequency identity"; thus, matching inoculum/sample pairs should exhibit a robust correlation signal. To achieve this, we conducted a pair-wise fit of multinomial distributions for all inocula against all (inocula + samples) using a classical method for multivariate datasets^{9,10}. We computed the correlation coefficients r^2 (depicted in Figure 1). We are aware that this correlation signal will tend to be lower with samples occurring after stringent bottleneck. Nonetheless several intriguing findings emerged from this analysis:

Firstly, a clear homogeneous group appeared (In09 to In24, AC19 to AC24). The correlations observed within this group ($r^2 > 0.65$) are significantly higher than those observed within the all-inocula or all-samples groups (non-parametric bootstrap confidence interval, $p < 0.05$). Moreover, these samples exhibit a distinct and unambiguous barcode identity, which is very easy to identify from the dataset

(absence of barcodes *new03* to *new06* and presence of barcode *new7*, as detailed in Table1 in Supplementary Material) that is incompatible with any other inocula or samples. We hypothesise that this group likely consists of technical replicates of the same sample or inoculum. Following this, a more in depth observation of the 7 new barcodes allowed us to identify two additional and mutually exclusive groups based on barcode identities: first group, presence of barcodes *new03* to *new06* and absence of *new07* (In01 to In07 in inocula) and second group, presence of all barcodes *new03* to *new07* (In08 in inocula). Provided that In08 is indeed a sample and not an inoculum (see section 3a), we suspect that samples originating from the later group (for example HW11, HW12 or HW21) do not have corresponding inocula in the provided raw dataset. Finally, there is a general heterogeneity in the correlations with only four inocula (In01, In04, In05, and In14) that match strongly with a majority of samples. As a side note, two of these four inocula have a significantly strong correlation (In01 and In05, $r^2 = 0.6534$). We hypothesise that In01 and In05 are technical replicates of the same inoculum. In view of these anomalies, we interpret that the provided dataset comes from at least three different experimental setups and that some samples were never provided with their corresponding inocula.

5) Are the conclusions of the study¹ still valid?

Our analysis led us into a particularly arduous task. Despite diligent efforts to rectify issues such as uncovering concealed barcodes, de-duplicating redundant barcodes, and mapping available raw reads, we find that the correspondence between inocula and samples remains highly ambiguous (see section 4). There is a significant likelihood of confusion between technical repetitions (such as probable re-sequencing) and biological repetitions. Consequently, we were unable to accurately re-calculate the bottleneck associated with the various biological contexts outlined¹.

Conclusion

After comprehensive examination, we have identified several significant shortcomings. Primarily, we noted the absence of crucial bacterial load data, insufficient number of biological repetitions, unacceptable data inflation due to duplications, and a general lack of clarity regarding data cleanup procedures and the association of inocula and samples.

We have endeavoured to present the facts impartially, leaving it to the journal editor and each reader of the study to discern whether these issues stem from honest oversights or potential lapses in research integrity.

We strongly recommend that the editorial board of *Nature Communications* request the authors to retract their article until all the aforementioned concerns have been thoroughly addressed. The integrity of the journal, the credibility of its publications, and, most importantly, the trustworthiness of the research presented are all at stake.

References

1. Jiang, G. *et al.* Effects of plant tissue permeability on invasion and population bottlenecks of a phytopathogen. *Nat. Commun.* **15**, 62 (2024).
2. Abel, S. *et al.* STAMP: Sequence tag-based analysis of microbial population dynamics. *Nat. Methods* **12**, 223 (2015).

3. Zhang, T. *et al.* Deciphering the landscape of host barriers to *Listeria monocytogenes* infection. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **114**, 6334–6339 (2017).
4. Liu, X. *et al.* Exploration of bacterial bottlenecks and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* pathogenesis by CRISPRi-seq. *Cell Host Microbe* **29**, 107-120.e6 (2021).
5. Hullahalli, K. & Waldor, M. K. Pathogen clonal expansion underlies multiorgan dissemination and organ-specific outcomes during murine systemic infection. *eLife* **10**, e70910.
6. Hullahalli, K., Dailey, K. G. & Waldor, M. K. Innate immune responses yield tissue-specific bottlenecks that scale with pathogen dose. *bioRxiv* 2023.06.09.543079 (2023)
doi:10.1101/2023.06.09.543079.
7. Campbell, I. W., Hullahalli, K., Turner, J. R. & Waldor, M. K. Quantitative dose-response analysis untangles host bottlenecks to enteric infection. *Nat. Commun.* **14**, 456 (2023).
8. Gillman, A. N., Mahmutovic, A., Abel zur Wiesch, P. & Abel, S. The Infectious Dose Shapes *Vibrio cholerae* Within-Host Dynamics. *mSystems* **6**, e00659-21.
9. Bergsma, W. A bias-correction for Cramér's V and Tschuprow's T. *J. Korean Stat. Soc.* **42**, 323–328 (2013).
10. Cramér, H. *Mathematical Methods of Statistics (PMS-9), Volume 9.* (1946).

Figure 1. Analysis of the identity of inocula (in Y axis) against all (inocula + samples) (in X axis). Heatmap of the pair-wise corrected Cramér's V correlation coefficient (r^2). A high value indicates a strong identity between the two compared inocula or samples.

Competing interest statement

NP identified himself as a former collaborator of Dr. Yong Zhang, one of the last authors of this paper. NP asserted that he made significant contributions to the inception of the present work by designing the original strategy, engaging in discussions regarding the results, and analysing sequencing data produced and supplied by Dr. Yong Zhang. NP had reservations regarding the readiness of this work for publication due to the insufficient replications and the absence of bacterial load data. It is important to note that all the content of this re-examination was drawn solely from the data within and accompanying the papers and does not rely on any prior data exchanged between NP and Dr. Yong Zhang during their collaboration.

Author contribution statement

SV and NP re-analysed all the raw data available as Supplementary Material of this paper. SV and NP discovered and discussed the many discrepancies between their analysis and the data presented in the paper. SV and NP wrote the paper.

Supplementary Material

Reference_read_30N.fasta

Template used for alignment of raw sequence reads and determination of new barcodes

New_barcodes.fasta

List of the curated 96 barcode sequences used for mapping and production of Table1

Table1.csv

Newly produced table of reads counts for each inocula and samples

Table2.csv

Table of correlation coefficients used for Figure 1

CRA010543.xlsx

Metadata file of raw data as downloaded from PRJCA016125, National Genomics Data Center of China

R_code_analysis.zip

Folder containing R code and data used in the analysis